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THE PECULIARITIES OF THE FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' SOFT SKILLS FORMATION DURING THEIR FOREIGN LANGUAGE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ФОРМУВАННЯ SOFT SKILLS У МАЙБУТНІХ УЧИТЕЛІВ ПОЧАТКОВОЇ ШКОЛИ ПІД ЧАС ІНШОМОВНОЇ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ ПІДГОТОВКИ

The purpose of the article is to reveal the peculiarities of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation during their foreign language professional training at the second (Master's) level of higher education.

Methodology. The theoretical methods (analysis, comparison, generalization and systematization of information); diagnostic methods (pedagogical observation, the survey of the applicants for the second (Master's) level of higher education of the 013 Primary education specialty, a specially worked out set of the tasks); methods of processing the received data for the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the results of the diagnostic research) have been used in the study.

Scientific novelty. The «soft skills» which must be formed in the future primary school teachers during their foreign language professional training have been classified; the peculiarities of the applicants' for the second (Master's) level of higher education of the 013 Primary education specialty «soft skills» formation on the basis of a specially worked out set of the communicatively oriented tasks within the «Foreign language (for professional purposes)» discipline have been revealed.

Conclusions. The future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation during their foreign language professional training must be on the basis of a specially worked out set of the tasks; meet the needs of the New Ukrainian school; be based on the student-centered approach, that will give the applicants for higher education the opportunity to fully reveal their communication, management, strategic, personal effectiveness skills and skills of effective information management.

Key words: soft skills, future primary school teachers, foreign language professional training, the second (Master's) level of higher education.

Мета статті – розкрити особливості формування «soft skills» у майбутніх учителів початкової школи у процесі їхньої іншомовної професійної підготовки на другому (магістерському) рівні вищої освіти.

Методологія. У дослідженні використано теоретичні методи (аналіз, порівняння, узагальнення і систематизація інформації); діагностичні (педагогічне спостереження, опитування здобувачів другого (магістерського) рівня вищої освіти спеціальності 013 Початкова освіта, спеціально розроблений комплекс вправ); методи обробки отриманих даних для кількісного і якісного аналізу результатів діагностичного дослідження.

Наукова новизна. У статті вперше розроблено класифікацію «soft skills», які мають бути сформовані у майбутніх учителів початкової школи у процесі їхньої іншомовної професійної підготовки; розкрито особливості формування «soft skills» у здобувачів другого (магістерського) рівня вищої освіти спеціальності 013 Початкова освіта на основі спеціально розробленого комплексу комунікативно спрямованих вправ у межах навчальної дисципліни «Іноземна мова (за професійним спрямуванням)».

Висновки. Формування «soft skills» у майбутніх учителів початкової школи у процесі їхньої іншомовної професійної підготовки має відбуватися на основі спеціально розробленого комплексу завдань; відповідати потребам Нової української школи; ґрунтуватися на студентоцентрованому підході, що надасть можливість здобувачам вищої освіти якнайповніше розкрити комунікативні, управлінські, стратегічні навички, навички особистої ефективності та ефективного управління інформацією.

Ключові слова: soft skills, м'які навички, майбутні вчителі початкової школи, іншомовна професійна підготовка, другий (магістерський) рівень вищої освіти.

The problem statement in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. Extremely strong competition in the labor market between potential applicants for a position indicates that a modern graduate of a higher educational institution to make a successful career, only thorough knowledge and practical experience is not enough, but the main requirement of modern society to the graduate is the ability to act independently, make quick decisions, realize the personal creative potential, be mobile, flexibly adapt to living conditions that are rapidly changing and developing.

Now employers pay a special attention not only to the high level of the potential employees' «hard skills» formation, which characterize not only professionally significant, narrowly focused qualifications, education and work experience, but also the level of their «soft skills» formation, which means a set of interprofessional, universal, social skills that determine effective participation in work and academic processes, the ability to interact effectively and relate to the culture of communication, regardless of the specialist's professional orientation (Shylova, 2017). Therefore, the orientation of education on the educational degrees applicants' «soft skills» formation is a priority in the formation of a professionally successful personality of a graduate of a higher educational institution, where a foreign language as a discipline has extraordinary potential.

The analysis of the basic researches and publications on the problem. The problem of «soft skills» formation is studied by

many scientists (O. Abashkina, O. Biliakovska, T. Blyzniuk, V. Davydova, N. Dluhunovych, L. Familiarska, E. Haiduchenko, O. Hlazunova, H. Ivonina, V. Korolchuk, K. Koval, K. Krutii, S. Nakhod, Y. Portland, L. Sebalo, O. Sosnytska, V. Sytnyk, A. Tiutiunyk, T. Voloshyna, N. Zhadko, and others). Thus, some of them considered the importance of «soft skills» for the professional development of future specialists in socionomic professions (S. Nakhod, 2018); made the classification of «soft skills» and studied the possibility of their development in students (K. Koval, 2015); studied the problem of «soft skills» in the system of the future IT-specialists' training (O. Hlazunova, T. Voloshyna, V. Korolchuk, 2019; N. Dluhunovych, 2014), as well as studied the development of these skills during the higher educational institutions students' foreign languages training (H. Kornius, 2020). In turn, O. Biliakovska considers «soft skills» as a necessary component of the future teachers' quality professional training in terms of competence approach (Biliakovska, 2018); T. Blyzniuk studies the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» development in the context of blended learning (Blyzniuk, 2021); L. Sebalo emphasizes that «soft skills» is a necessary component of the future primary school teachers' successful training on the Bachelor's degree (Sebalo, 2021).

However, the problem of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation during their foreign language professional training for obtaining the Master's degree has not been covered by the scientists.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the peculiarities of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation during their foreign language professional training for obtaining the Master's degree.

The coverage of the procedure of theoretical and methodological and experimental research. The theoretical methods (analysis, comparison, generalization and systematization of information); diagnostic (pedagogical observation, survey of students, doing a specially worked out set of the tasks by the students); statistical (methods of processing personal data for quantitative and qualitative analysis of the results of the diagnostic research) have been used in the study.

The presentation of the basic material of the research with the obtained scientific results grounding. Let us reveal the basic concepts of the study. As a skill is defined as «a mental neoplasm through which an individual is able to perform a certain action rationally, with proper accuracy and speed, without unnecessary expenditure of physical and neuropsychological energy» (Voitok, 1982, p. 98), in this particular case, «skills» should be interpreted as «a person's ability to master difficult-to-control actions» (Claxton, Guy, Costa, & Kallick, 2016, pp. 60–64).

The scientists define «soft skills» as a set of non-specialized, super-professional skills that are responsible for successful participation in the work process, high productivity and, unlike specialized skills, are comprehensive and not related to a specific field (Smahina, 2017, p. 21); desirable qualities for certain forms of employment that do not depend on the acquired knowledge: they include common sense, the ability to have relationships with people and a positive flexible attitude (Soft skills: 7 important skills...); belong to sociological terms and are unified skills and personal qualities that increase work efficiency and interaction with people.

The concept of the «professional training» in pedagogical science is defined as professional studying, the process of the future specialists' mastering the knowledge, skills and abilities that will be necessary for their professional activity; the system of the vocational education, the purpose of which is to acquire the skills by the students necessary to perform a particular job (Pedagogical Encyclopedic Dictionary, 2003, p. 223), as well as the process of acquiring the knowledge, skills, abilities by the future specialists that will enable them to work in the chosen professional field. However, it should be noted that the professional training of a specialist, in particular a future teacher, cannot be limited only to the procedural side. The purposeful educational activity, the activity of the participants of the learning process, which

will ensure the formation and development of the future teacher's professional and socially significant qualities, is also integral. Therefore, we define the «professional training» as a system of organizational, methodological and pedagogical activities, during which the formation of personality, professional orientation, knowledge, skills and professional readiness will be carried out. Taking this definition as a basis, the future primary school teachers' «professional training» is defined as a holistic pedagogical system, the functioning of which involves creating optimal conditions for the development of the teacher's personality based on mastering the necessary knowledge, skills, competencies, professional, personal qualities, which will ensure the effectiveness of his future pedagogical work; a holistic, dynamic pedagogical system capable for self-development, characterized by the specific patterns, unity of the content, goals and means, aimed at forming the future teacher's professional competence, general and professional culture, creative thinking and his readiness for professional self-development (Mysechko, 2008).

The important components of the future teachers' professional training are the complexes of «hard skills» and «soft skills», which will be able to ensure the successful implementation of the professional work and help them to always be in demand in the labor market.

In our opinion, the terms of «hard skills» and «soft skills» should be considered from the standpoint of the competency approach. Therefore, «hard skills» can be considered as «basic competencies», which is the integration of knowledge, experience, professionally significant personal qualities that contribute to achieving high results in the process of professional work; such competencies can be clearly demonstrated. Thus, the future primary school teachers' «hard skills» include a system of the professional competencies that combine general didactic and special professional knowledge, system of professional skills, professional abilities and professionally significant personality traits (Nakhod, 2013, pp. 52–53). In turn, «soft skills» are understood as «flexibility», lack of stereotypes, the ability to change, the willingness, ability and capability of a person to act in any changing situations, based on her own experience and intuition (Nakhod, 2013, p. 54). Therefore, we believe that future specialists, especially primary school teachers, should have a high level of «soft skills» formation, because the work in the «person-person» system is focused on other people, especially since it requires the direct contact with young children, and therefore unpredictable, and is associated with the lack of the only and rigid algorithms, requirements, technologies for the process of the professional work.

Summarizing the above, it should be noted that the basis of «hard skills» are the competencies, the components of which are the professional knowledge, skills, abilities and experience; are formed with less effort, compared to «soft skills», and guaranteed results (under the condition of compliance with the basic criteria such as motivation, the ability to learn, etc.); their development is much faster than the development of «soft skills»; practically have no ability to the reverse development; are used in standard terms and are important in the short prospect. In contrast, the basis of «soft skills» are the competencies that cover relevant patterns of behavior, personal values; are formed with greater effort, compared to «hard skills», and without a guarantee of achieving the required level (limit of competencies, deep integration into the structure of a personality); their development is slower compared to the development of «hard skills»; under specific conditions have the ability to the reverse development; are used in standard and changing conditions and are important in the long prospect.

However, since the purpose of our study is to reveal the peculiarities of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation during their foreign language training for obtaining the Master's degree, we consider it appropriate to take as a basis for the specialists' «soft skills» formation who are trained on the educational and professional 013 Primary education syllabus of the second (Master's) level of higher education, 01 Education/Pedagogy field of knowledge, the program competencies, as they fully reflect the full range of skills and abilities to be acquired by the future primary school. Thus, *the integrated competence* is comprehensive (the ability to competently solve complex problems and problems in the field of primary education, which involves research and innovative professional work in the industrial situations characterized by the uncertainty of conditions).

Concerning *the general competencies (GC)*, it is expedient to take into account all of them, because they are basic:

GC1. The ability to act socially responsible and consciously.

GC2. The ability to generate new ideas.

GC3. The ability to conduct research on an appropriate level.

GC4. The ability to learn and master modern knowledge.

GC 5. The ability to work in a team.

GC6. The ability to search, process and analyze information from various sources.

GC7. The ability to appreciate and respect the diversity and multiculturalism.

GC8. The ability to communicate in a foreign language in specific areas and situations.

Among *the professional competencies (PC)*, the formation of which will ensure the full development of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» during their foreign language training for obtaining the Master's degree, we consider it appropriate to distinguish the following:

PC1. The ability to design the educational process in elementary classes with a variety of psychological, pedagogical, methodological factors; anticipate the possible consequences of their use.

PC2. The ability to organize the educational process in elementary classes using traditional and innovative technologies, methods, techniques and funds.

PC3. The ability to analyze, critically evaluate, compare facts, phenomena, experience updating theory and educational practices in different countries.

PC4. The ability to conduct, analyze, interpret and design the results of psychological and pedagogical research.

PC5. The ability to partner interaction with participants in the educational process.

PC 6. The ability to monitor activities in primary school.

PC7. The ability to provide methodological assistance to colleagues on training, development, education and socialization of primary school students.

PC8. The ability to navigate the relevant problems of formation of English communicative competence of the primary school teacher.

Having made a detailed analysis of the program competencies, as well as the program learning outcomes, which reflect the full range of skills and abilities to be acquired by the future primary school teachers, we conclude that the «soft skills» that we have distinguished based on the competencies prescribed by the 013 Primary education syllabus of the second (Master's) level of higher education and which can be formed during the future primary school teachers' foreign language training, it is expedient to classify according to the following groups of skills:

- 1) personal effectiveness skills;
- 2) communication skills;
- 3) management skills;
- 4) strategic skills;
- 5) skills of effective information management.

We present the classification of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» required, the training of whom is carried out by the second (Master's) level of higher education, in order to successfully and effectively implement their further professional work in Table 1.

The classification of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills»

#	Groups of «soft skills»	Types of «soft skills»
1.	Personal effectiveness skills	The skills to act socially responsibly and consciously in decision--making
		The skills to focus on achieving goals / success
		The skills to feel self-reliance
		The skills to take a positive aim
		The skills to make objective self-appraisal
		The skills to make self-improvement
		The skills to resist failures / stress resistance
		The skills to make self-organization and self-motivation
		The skills to empathize
		The skills to dedicate
		The skills to resist criticism
		The skills to solve problems wisely and find the most rational solution in each specific situation
		The skills to resolve conflict situations and provide support in new, problematic and crisis situations
		The skills to show determination in decision making
		The skills to work in stressful situations and the skills to distribute time wisely, forcing it to work for oneself
2.	Communication skills	The skills to communicate in a foreign language in specific areas and situations
		The skills to master a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure the effectiveness of the English-language communicative process, to master the technique of communication in English
		The skills to speak, make messages and reports
		The skills to appreciate and respect diversity and multiculturalism
		The skills to partner interaction with participants in the educational process
		The skills to master certain norms of communication, standards, stereotypes of speech behavior
		The skills to speak and be understood by others
		The skills to be persuasive and influential during speeches, discussions and negotiations, thoughtfully looking for solutions that will satisfy all parties
		The skills to reach understanding with others
		The skills to hear, not just listen
The skills to communicate with parents, colleagues, other professionals to support pupils		
3.	Management skills	The skills to show leadership qualities (not so much the skills to lead as the skills to wisely motivate others)
		The skills to show initiative
		The skills to work in a team
		The skills to organize the educational process on the basis of partnership between all participants (pupils, teacher, parents)
		The skills to set urgent tasks
		The skills to carry out monitoring work in primary school

#	Groups of «soft skills»	Types of «soft skills»
4.	Strategic skills	The skills to design the educational process in elementary classes with a variety of psychological, pedagogical, methodological factors; anticipate the possible consequences of their use
		The skills to organize the educational process in elementary classes using traditional and innovative technologies, methods, techniques and funds
		The skills to identify the conditions for the effectiveness of pedagogical activities and take them into account in the organization of their own work on the basis of knowledge about the state and trends of modern education
		The skills to generate new ideas
5.	Skills of effective information management	The skills to learn and master modern knowledge
		The skills to search, analyze, process and systematization of scientific and professional information from various sources (modern computer tools, cloud technologies, databases)
		The skills to show flexibility (adaptability, skills to learn, openness to the new)
		The skills to analyze, critically evaluate, compare facts, phenomena, experience updating theory and educational practices in different countries of the world / identify patterns and trends in education in different countries of the world
		The skills to conduct research on an appropriate level
		The skills to conduct, analyze, interpret and design the results of psychological and pedagogical research

In order to determine the level of the future applicants' for the second (Master's) level of higher education of the 013 Primary education specialty «soft skills» formation during their foreign language training, we conducted the survey, which provided a reflexive determination of the students' skills to analyze their own pedagogical work, because it is the reflexive assessment of the opportunities / qualities by the personality that is able to most vividly reflect the inner feelings of the person himself, and hence the level of confident mastery of certain skills.

The survey was conducted at the beginning of the students' studying on the educational and professional 013 Primary education syllabus for obtaining the second (Master's) level of higher education and aimed to determine the initial level of their «soft skills» formation that were to be formed during their training for obtaining the Bachelor's degree. 45 students of the full-time and correspondence departments took part in the survey. The students were asked to rate the degree of revealing / formation of their «soft skills» proposed in Table 1 from 1 to 10 points.

According to the results of the initial survey, the arithmetic mean of the level of the future applicants' for the second (Master's) level of higher education the personal effectiveness skills formation in a percentage correlation was 77%: the future specialists rated their skills to resist failures the lowest – at 66.4%, as well as the skills to feel self-reliance – at 66.8%, the highest – the skills to act socially responsibly

and consciously in decision-making – at 93.2%, as well as the skills to empathize – at 90.7%;

communication skills – 78.9%: the applicants rated their skills to be persuasive and influential during speeches, discussions and negotiations, thoughtfully looking for solutions that will satisfy all parties the lowest – at 70.4%, the highest – the skills to hear, not just listen – at 85.7%;

management skills – 74.4%: the future primary school teachers rated their skills to show initiative the lowest – at 69.6%, the highest – the skills to work in a team – at 83.2%;

strategic skills – 75.6%: the future specialists rated their skills to generate new ideas the lowest – at 73.3%, the highest – the skills to organize the educational process in elementary classes using traditional and innovative technologies, methods, techniques and funds – at 78.9%;

skills of effective information management – 76.1%: the applicants rated their skills to analyze, critically evaluate, compare facts, phenomena, experience updating theory and educational practices in different countries of the world / identify patterns and trends in education in different countries of the world the lowest – at 76.5%, the highest – the skills to search, analyze, process and systematization of scientific and professional information from various sources (modern computer tools, cloud technologies, databases) – at 82.7%.

Since the purpose of our research is to study the peculiarities of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» during their foreign language professional training, in order

to form the skills mentioned above they were offered a specially worked out set of the communicatively oriented tasks within the «Foreign language (for professional purposes)» discipline, which would maximally contribute to the formation of all groups of the future applicants' for the second (Master's) level of higher education of the 013 Primary education specialty «soft skills» (the scope of the discipline was 7 lectures and 8 practical classes). Here are some examples of them.

Task 1. The social role of a person in the society depends upon the amount of esteem, admiration and approval we get from the society. Describe the requirements of the society for the personality of a teacher.

Task 2. A headmistress constantly focuses her teachers' attention on their manner of dressing and hairstyle. What do you think what requirements for the primary school teachers' appearance she makes? Why?

Task 3. Your child is to go to school this year. You are not sure whom of the teachers to entrust your child to. You ask your friend for advice.

Task 4. You are a primary school headmistress who is responsible for the staff. A graduate of the Faculty of Preschool and Primary Education and Arts has applied. How would you substantiate your choice to employ him?

Task 5. You are a primary school teacher. Before the lesson you had an unpleasant talk. How should it tell on your conducting the lesson?

Task 6. Your child is to go to school this year. You are not sure what type of school to choose for your child. You ask your close friend for advice.

Task 7. You are the Minister of Education and Science of Ukraine. What changes would you make in today's system of primary education if you had such an opportunity? Why?

Task 8. You are the representatives of one Ukrainian school. You are going to take part in the international contest on working out the best School Charter. What are the key points of it that will differ your school from others' and that will give you the opportunity to win?

Task 9. You are a Methodist teacher and you are responsible for making changes in the school curriculum concerning teaching lower-attaining pupils. What changes would you make and why?

Task 10. Being a graduate of the Faculty of Preschool and Primary Education and Arts you will have a pretty good idea what kind of punishment can be applied to young learners in the case of their misbehavior. What can it be?

How to prevent pupils' misbehavior at the lessons?

Task 11. Sometimes in some Ukrainian primary schools pupils suffer from their teachers' cruelty. What are the reasons of it? Are there any laws adopted in our country according to which teachers are punished for such mistreatment?

Task 12. You are a young primary school teacher and you have been asked to replace the main teacher in one of the primary school forms. The pupils seeing unknown teacher are trying to show their utter disrespect for you. What are your actions?

Task 13. You are a primary school teacher. You have been teaching one child for quite a long period of time and see that he is not still making the grade. What would you do in order to encourage him / her?

Task 14. A young teacher makes obvious mistakes in conducting the lessons. What can they be? Being a more experienced teacher, give her / him reasonably fair pieces of advice how to avoid such mistakes in the future.

Task 15. Nowadays learning foreign languages is becoming more and more popular in our country, because every parent wants his child to get proper education. At the same time language teachers continue to discuss the means to improve the ease and effectiveness of language learning through modifications in their ways of teaching. What are the modern approaches to teaching young learners foreign languages?

Task 16. Read the texts about the job responsibilities of primary school teachers in England and correlate them with those that our primary school teachers have. Are there any differences? What is it caused by?

Task 17. You've got a good chance to educate your child abroad. Would you make use of the opportunity? Why?

Task 18. While working as a primary school teacher you see no point in wasting either time or effort doing what? Make a list.

Task 19. This year you are going to take part in the contest «The best teacher of the year». What are your steps in achieving this rank? Get ready to do your best to prove that you are really deserve this rank.

Task 20. Write an instructive letter to the future generations of primary school teachers concerning teaching young learners. Try to give reasonable pieces of advice.

The description of the basic material of the research with the obtained scientific results grounding.

At the end of studying the «Foreign language (for professional purposes)» discipline

the applicants for the second (Master's) level of higher education of the 013 Primary Education specialty was offered a reflexive survey to determine the level of their different groups of «soft skills» formation according to table 1 again.

The results of the final survey confirmed an increase in the level of the future applicants' for the second (Master's) level of higher education «soft skills» of all groups formation. Thus, the arithmetic mean of the level of the future teachers' personal effectiveness skills formation in a percentage correlation was already 86.5%: the future graduates rated their skills to resist failures a little higher – at 82%, the skills to feel self-reliance – at 78%, the skills to act socially responsibly and consciously in decision-making – at 95%, and the skills to empathize – at 92%;

communication skills – 87.4%: the applicants rated their skills to be persuasive and influential during speeches, discussions and negotiations, thoughtfully looking for solutions that will satisfy all parties at 78%, and the skills to hear, not just listen – at 92%;

management skills – 86%: the future primary school teachers rated their skills to show initiative at 87%, and the skills to work in a team – at 92%;

strategic skills – 86.3%: the future specialists rated their skills to generate new ideas at 78%, and the skills to organize the educational process in elementary classes using traditional and innovative technologies, methods, techniques and funds – at 90%;

skills of effective information management – 86.5%: the applicants rated their skills to analyze, critically evaluate, compare facts, phenomena, experience updating theory and educational practices in different countries of the world / identify patterns and trends in education in different countries of the world at 82%, and the skills to search, analyze, process and systematization of scientific and professional information from various sources (modern computer tools, cloud technologies, databases) – at 93%.

We present the dynamics of the level of the future applicants' for the Master's degree of the 013 Primary Education specialty «soft skills» formation in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of the level of the future applicants' for the Master's degree of the 013 Primary Education specialty «soft skills» formation

The main reason for the somewhat low results of the initial survey to determine the level of the future applicants' for the Master's degree of the 013 Primary Education specialty «soft skills» formation was the future primary school specialists' uncertainty about their skills

to demonstrate their language and speech knowledge and skills in a foreign language in the professional work at the appropriate level and the skills to discuss the topics in a foreign language, prescribed by the educational syllabus, which served as a kind of a

psychological barrier to the revealing of their «soft skills». This specificity of students' mastering a foreign language was traced during their further studying the program material within the «Foreign language (for professional purposes)» discipline, which also partially affected the results of the level of all groups of «soft skills» formation.

The conclusions on the study and the prospects for further researches in this direction. Having examined the employers' requirements to the potential applicants for a position, we come to the conclusion that, in addition to the specialists' «hard skills» formation at the appropriate level, which characterize their professionally significant, narrowly focused qualifications, education and work experience, non-specialized, super-professional «soft skills» that are responsible for successful participation in the work process and high productivity are also extremely demanded for successful self-realization in the labor market.

Having clearly distinguished the concepts of «hard skills» and «soft skills», we in order to study the types of «soft skills» to be formed in the future applicants for the second (Master's) level of higher education of the 013 Primary education specialty in detail, we classified them into the following groups: 1) personal effectiveness skills; 2) communication skills; 3) management skills; 4) strategic skills; 5) skills of effective information management.

In order to increase the efficiency of the process of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation within the «Foreign language (for professional purposes)» discipline they were offered a specially worked out set of the communicatively oriented tasks to form «soft skills» of all the groups mentioned above.

The results of the future primary school specialists' final survey testified, as for such a relatively short period of time, a significant increase in the level of all groups of «soft skills» formation, which proved the effectiveness of the worked out for this purpose set of the tasks.

But, in our opinion, the effectiveness of the process of the applicants' for the second (Master's) level of higher education on the educational and professional 013 Primary

education syllabus all groups of «soft skills» formation will be much higher under the condition of a holistic mastery of the skills and qualities that must be formed within the disciplines prescribed by the syllabus.

Thus, among the peculiarities of the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation during their foreign language professional training for obtaining the Master's degree it is advisable to distinguish the following:

1) «soft skills» formation should take place on the basis of the integrated, general and professional competencies prescribed by the educational and professional 013 Primary education syllabus of the second (Master's) level of higher education;

2) «hard skills» and «soft skills» formation should be holistic and integrated when studying both the disciplines of the normative cycle and disciplines of the students' free choice;

3) the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation during their foreign language professional training should be based on the specially worked out sets of the tasks;

4) the future primary school teachers' «soft skills» formation should take place in accordance with the school concept, meet the needs of the New Ukrainian school;

5) «soft skills» formation should take place from the standpoint of student-centeredness, which will enable the applicants' for higher education to fully reveal their personal effectiveness skills, communication skills, management skills, strategic skills and skills of effective information management;

6) «soft skills» formation should take place under the condition of providing the possibility of the mutual assessment and reflexive self-assessment of the level of the «soft skills» formation by the applicants' for the Master's degree on the 013 Primary education specialty during their foreign language training.

We see the prospects of our further research in an integrated disciplinary study of the peculiarities of the future primary school specialists' «soft skills» formation in order to ensure their further successful professional work.

Список використаних джерел

- Біляковська, О. (2018). «Soft skills» як необхідна складова якісної професійної підготовки майбутнього вчителя. Відновлено з http://212.87.236.17:8080/Content/5918/14_Biljakowska_Rocznik_20.pdf.
- Близнюк, Т. (2021). *Розвиток soft skills майбутніх учителів початкової школи в умовах змішаного навчання: простір можливостей*. Відновлено з https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_3p3j8T2kEAQrnDaQZnvvSuDIw3L-OiP/view.

- Войток, В. І. (Ред.). (1982). *Психологічний словник*. Київ: Вища школа.
- Глазунова, О. Г., Волошина, Т. В., & Корольчук, В. І. (2019). *Розвиток «Soft skills» у майбутніх фахівців з інформаційних технологій: методи, засоби, індикатори оцінювання*. Відновлено з <https://openedu.kubg.edu.ua/journal/index.php/openedu/article/view/256/pdf>.
- Длугунович, Н. А. (2014). Soft skills як необхідна складова підготовки ІТ-фахівців. *Вісник Хмельницького національного університету*. Вип. 6 (219), 239–242.
- Коваль, К. О. (2015). Розвиток «soft skills» у студентів – один з важливих чинників працевлаштування. *Вісник Вінницького політехнічного університету*, 2, 162–167.
- Корнюш, Г. В. (2020). Формування м'яких навичок у студентів закладів вищої освіти в контексті навчання іноземних мов. *Викладання мов у вищих навчальних закладах освіти*, Вип. 36. 99–110.
- Мисечко, О. Є. (2008). *Формування системи фахової підготовки вчителів іноземної мови у педагогічних навчальних закладах України (початок ХХ ст. – початок 1960-х рр.): монографія*. Житомир: Полісся.
- Наход, С. А. (2018). Значущість «soft skills» для професійного становлення майбутніх фахівців соціономічних професій. *Науковий часопис національного педагогічного університету імені М.П. Драгоманова, Серія 5, Вип. 63*, 131–135.
- Наход, С. А. (2013). Прогнозування в професійній діяльності майбутнього психолога. *Наукові записки НДУ ім. М. Гоголя, Вип. 3*, 52–53.
- Педагогический энциклопедический словарь*. (2003). Москва: Высшая школа.
- Себало, Л. (2021). *Soft skills – необхідна складова успішної підготовки майбутнього вчителя початкової школи*. Відновлено з <https://ojs.ukrlogos.in.ua/index.php/conferences/article/view/11104>.
- Смагіна, Т. М. (2017). Зміщення акцентів з *hard skills* на *soft skills* в підвищенні професійної компетентності педагогів у системі післядипломної освіти. В. О. Пастовенський (Ред.), *Розвиток професійної компетентності педагогів у системі післядипломної педагогічної освіти регіону: збірник матеріалів конференції*. (с. 21). Житомир.
- Шилова, С. А. (2017). Формирование гибких навыков средствами микрогрупповых форм работы при обучении иностранному языку в вузе. *Известия Саратовского университета: сб. науч. тр. Саратов: Саратовский ун-т. Сер. Акмеология образования. Психология развития, Вип. 4 (24)*, 374–380.
- Claxton, Guy, Costa, A., & Kallick, Bena (2016). Hard thinking about soft skills. *Educational Leadership. Vol. 73, 6*, 60–64.
- Soft skills: 7 важных навыков для любой профессии*. Відновлено з <https://thepoint.rabota.ua/soft-skills-7-vazhnyh-navykov-dlya-lyuboy-professyy>.

References

- Biliakovska, O. (2018). «Soft skills» yak neobkhidna skladova yakisnoi profesiinoi pidhotovky maibutnoho vchytelia [«Soft skills» as a necessary component of the qualified primary school teacher's professional training]. Retrieved from http://212.87.236.17:8080/Content/5918/14_Biljakowska_Rocznik_20.pdf.
- Blyzniuk, T. (2021). *Rozvytok soft skills maibutnikh uchyteliv pochatkovoї shkoly v umovakh zmishanoho navchannia: prostir mozhlyvostei [Development of the future primary school teachers' soft skills in the context of blended learning: a space of opportunities]*. Retrieved from https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_3p3j8T2kEAQrmdaQZnvvSuDIw3L-OiP/view.
- Dlahunovych, N. A. (2014). Soft skills yak neobkhidna skladova pidhotovky IT-fakhivtsiv [Soft skills as a necessary part of IT-specialists' training]. *Visnyk Khmelnytskoho natsionalnoho universytetu – Bulletin of Khmelnytskyi National University*, 6 (219), 239–242.
- Voitok, V. I. (Ed.). (1982). *Psykhologichnyi slovnyk [Psychological dictionary]*. Kyiv: Vyshcha Shkola.
- Hlazunova, O. H., Voloshyna, T. V., & Korolchuk, V. I. (2019). *Rozvytok «Soft skills» u maibutnikh fakhivtsiv z informatsiinykh tekhnolohii: metody, zasoby, indykatory otsiniuvannia [Future information technology specialists' «soft skills» formation: methods, tools, evaluation indicators]*. Retrieved from <https://openedu.kubg.edu.ua/journal/index.php/openedu/article/view/256/pdf>.
- Koval, K. O. (2015). *Rozvytok «soft skills» u studentiv – odyin z vazhlyvykh chynnykiv pratsevlashtuvannia [The development of «soft skills» in students is one of the important factors*

- of employment]. *Visnyk Vinnytskoho politekhnichnoho universytetu – Bulletin of Vinnytsia Polytechnic University*, 2, 162-167.
- Korniush, H. V. (2020). Formuvannia miakykh navychok u studentiv zakladiv vyshchoi osvity v konteksti navchannia inozemnykh mov [Higher educational institutions students' soft skills formation in the context of learning foreign languages]. *Vykladannia mov u vyshchyykh navchalnykh zakladakh osvity – Teaching languages in higher educational institutions*, 36, 99–110.
- Mysechko, O. Ye. (2008). *Formuvannia systemy fakhovoi pidhotovky vchyteliv inozemnoi mowy u pedahohichnykh navchalnykh zakladakh Ukrainy (pochatok XX st. – pochatok 1960-kh rr.): monohrafiia* [Formation of the system of the foreign language teachers' professional training in the pedagogical educational institutions of Ukraine (beginning of the XX century – beginning of the 1960s)]: monograph. Zhytomyr: Polissia.
- Nakhod, S. A. (2018). Znachushchist «soft skills» dlia profesinoho stanovlennia maibutnikh fakhivtsiv sotsionomichnykh profesii [The importance of «soft skills» for the professional development of future professionals in socioeconomic professions]. *Naukovyi chasopys imeni M.P. Drahomanova – M.P. Drahomanov scientific journal, Series 5*, 63, 131-135.
- Nakhod, S. A. (2013). Prohnozuvannia v profesiinii diialnosti maibutnoho psykholoha [Forecasting in the professional work of the future psychologist]. *Naukovi zapysky NDU im. M. Hoholia – Scientific notes of Nizhyn Mykola Gogol State University*, 3, 52–53.
- Pedagogicheskij encyklopedicheskij slovar [Pedagogical encyclopedic dictionary]*. (2003). Moscow: Vysshaya shkola.
- Sebalo, L. (2021). *Soft skills – neobkhidna skladova uspishnoi pidhotovky maibutnoho vchytelia pochatkovoї shkoly* [Soft skills is a necessary component of future primary school teacher's successful training]. Retrieved from <https://ojs.ukrlogos.in.ua/index.php/conferences/article/view/11104>.
- Smahina, T. M. (2017). *Zmishchennia aktsentiv z hard skills na soft skills v pidvyshchenni profesiinoї kompetentnosti pedahohiv u systemi pisladyplomnoi osvity* [Shifting the emphasis from hard skills to soft skills in improving the teachers' professional competence in the system of postgraduate education]. In O. V. Pastovenskii (Ed.). *Rozvytok profesiinoї kompetentnosti pedahohiv u systemi pisladyplomnoi pedahohichnoi osvity rehionu: zbirnyk materialiv konferentsii – Development of teachers' professional competence in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education of the region: a collection of conference materials*. (p. 21). Zhytomyr.
- Shylova, S. A. (2017). Formirovanie gibkikh navykov sredstvami mikrogruppovykh form raboty pri obuchenii inostrannomu yazyku v vuze [Soft skills formation by means of microgroup forms of work while teaching a foreign language in a higher educational institution]. *Izvestiya Saratovskogo universiteta: sb. nauch. tr. – Bulletin of Saratov University: Collection of scientific works*. Saratov: Saratov University. Ser. Akmeologiya obrazovaniya. *Psikhologiya razvitiya*, 4 (24), 374–380.
- Claxton, Guy, Costa, A., & Kallick, Bena (2016). Hard thinking about soft skills. *Educational Leadership*, Vol. 73, 6, 60–64.
- Soft skills: 7 vazhnykh navykov dlya lyuboy professii [7 important skills for any profession]*. Retrieved from <https://thepoint.rabota.ua/soft-skills-7-vazhnykh-navykov-dlya-lyuboy-professyy>.

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